

Attitudes, Sentiments, And Concerns In Inclusive Education: A Quantitative Causal-Comparative Analysis Of General And Special Educators In India

Sujay Ranjan Chaudhuri*

Army Institute of Management Kolkata (India)

ABSTRACT

Background: Many people believe that inclusive education is crucial to achieving an equitable and egalitarian society. In order to successfully implement inclusive education in mainstream schools, general teachers and special educators are important stakeholders whose attitudes, sentiments, and concerns are crucial. Therefore, it was considered imperative to determine whether general teachers and special educators differ significantly in their attitudes, sentiments, and concerns about the adoption of inclusive education in India.

Purpose: The study aimed to examine whether significant differences exist between general teachers and special educators with respect to their attitudes, sentiments, and concerns regarding the implementation of inclusive education in India.

Method: A quantitative causal-comparative research design was employed to address the stated objective.

Results: The findings revealed significant differences in attitudes, sentiments, and concerns between general teachers and special educators, with special educators demonstrating more positive attitudes, sentiments, and concerns toward inclusive education than their general teacher counterparts.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Attitudes, Sentiments, Concerns, General Teachers, Special Educators

INTRODUCTION

Education is widely acknowledged as a powerful instrument for advancing social justice and equity. Within this broader framework, inclusive education is regarded as essential for the realization of an equitable society (Brig (Dr) Sujay Ranjan Chaudhuri (Retd), 2026b). Although the concept has gained substantial acceptance across industrialized nations, many education systems continue to face challenges in identifying and implementing appropriate frameworks that effectively serve all learners (Shaffer & Thomas-Brown, 2015a). Despite sustained policy-level emphasis, the pace of implementation remains inadequate relative to the targets established under SDG-4.

The transition toward inclusive education has been impeded by multiple barriers, among which attitudinal constraints among key stakeholders—particularly general teachers and special educators—are especially significant. As noted by Hussey et al.,

(2017), attitudinal factors lie at the core of implementation challenges, with positive attitudes being recognized as a crucial determinant of successful inclusion (Florian & Spratt, 2013). Teachers play a pivotal role in fostering an inclusive and supportive classroom environment for all learners (Costello & Boyle, 2013a). Consequently, their attitudes toward integration and inclusion have been extensively examined over several decades due to their critical influence on educational practice (Saloviita, 2020b). Empirical evidence suggests that, while teachers generally hold favourable views toward inclusion, these attitudes are shaped by factors such as the severity of students' disabilities, the extent of in-service training, prior experience with Children with Special Needs (CwSN), and contextual environmental variables (Avramidis et al., 2000).

Given that attitudes toward inclusion are predictive of the intention to adopt and sustain inclusive practices in mainstream classrooms, it is essential to systematically assess these attitudes in order to

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

identify and address barriers to effective policy implementation (Ewing et al., 2018). A comprehensive understanding of teachers' attitudes constitutes a foundational step in the design and evaluation of interventions aimed at promoting inclusive practices for CwSN (Livneh et al., 2000). Furthermore, attitudes toward CwSN are inherently multidimensional (Nowicki & Sandieson, 2002); therefore, the use of psychometrically robust instruments is necessary to examine potential differences in attitudes, sentiments, and concerns between general teachers and special educators regarding the implementation of inclusive education in India.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is a multidimensional construct encompassing the recognition and appreciation of diversity, alongside commitments to human rights, social justice, and equity. It is further informed by the social model of disability and a broader socio-political perspective on education (Garry Hornby, 2014). The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016 defines inclusive education as a system in which students with and without disabilities learn together, with teaching-learning processes appropriately adapted to address the diverse needs of learners with disabilities (Schuelka et al., 2020). Additionally, inclusive education emphasizes collaborative engagement and partnership between students and teachers (Shutaleva et al., 2023).

Attitudes

Attitude is a psychological construct referring to an individual's predisposition toward engaging in a particular activity (De Boer et al., 2011). It has also been conceptualized as the manner in which individuals perceive and evaluate the world around them, including other people, objects, behaviours, and institutional norms (Hill et al., 1977).

Sentiments

Sentiments refer to teachers' levels of comfort and emotional orientation toward individuals with disabilities (Shields, 2020a).

Concerns

Concerns include a strong interest or regard for, as well as apprehension or fear about, establishing inclusive educational approaches (Brig (Dr) Sujay Ranjan Chaudhuri (Retd), 2026a).

General teacher

The general teacher of record for general education, co-teach, and inclusion classes who is a highly qualified content expert (Shaffer & Thomas-Brown, 2015b).

Special educators

According to Individuals with Disabilities in Education Act 2004 (IDEA), special educator is a teacher with a minimum of a bachelor's degree and state certification in special education who is knowledgeable of disabilities (Shields, 2020b). Special educators (also called resource teachers) are a group of teachers who are trained to teach students with disabilities (NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY: Opportunities & Challenges A White Paper on India's National Education Policy and Disability Inclusive Education National Centre for Promotion of Employment for Disabled People, n.d.).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Objective

The study sought to examine whether significant differences exist between general teachers and special educators with respect to their attitudes, sentiments, and concerns regarding the implementation of inclusive education in India.

Research Question

The study addressed the following research question:

To what extent, if any, do general teachers and special educators differ in their attitudes, sentiments, and concerns toward the implementation of inclusive education in India?

Hypotheses

H₀ (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant difference between general teachers and special educators in their attitudes, sentiments, and concerns regarding the implementation of inclusive education in India.

H₁ (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant difference between general teachers and special educators in their attitudes, sentiments, and concerns regarding the implementation of inclusive education in India.

Research Design

A quantitative causal-comparative research design was employed to examine the factors influencing the attitudes, sentiments, and concerns of general teachers and special educators toward the implementation of inclusive education.

Instrument Used

Data for the study were collected using the *Sentiments, Attitudes, and Concerns about Inclusive Education Revised (SACIE-R)* scale (Forlin et al., 2011). The validity of the instrument was established through a sample of 542 pre-service teachers drawn from nine institutions across four countries—Canada, Hong Kong, India, and the United States. The scale demonstrated acceptable reliability, with a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.74 (Loreman et al., 2013). Furthermore, a review by Ewing et al., (2018) identified the SACIE-R as a robust instrument with sound psychometric properties for assessing attitudes toward inclusive education (Opoku et al., 2021).

The SACIE-R comprises 15 items categorized into three dimensions: sentiments, attitudes, and concerns (Opoku et al., 2021). The *Sentiments* dimension evaluates respondents’ comfort levels in interactions with Children with Special Needs (CwSN); the *Attitudes* dimension assesses acceptance of such students; and the *Concerns* dimension captures apprehensions related to the implementation of inclusive education (Loreman et al., 2007). Items 2, 5, 9, 11, and 13 correspond to the sentiments dimension; items 3, 6, 8, 9, 12, and 15 pertain to attitudes; and items 1, 4, 7, 10, and 14 relate to concerns. Responses were recorded on a four-point Likert scale comprising the options: Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Agree, and Strongly Agree.

Psychometric characteristics of instrument

Table 1 displays the psychometric characteristics for the three scale scores. The Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficients ranged from $\alpha = .73$ to $\alpha = .76$, which were calculated using following formula:

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{k - 1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum V_i}{V_t} \right)$$

Table 1. The Cronbach’s alpha values

Variables	Description	Values	Internal Consistency
Sentiments			
k	Number of items	5	Acceptable
$\sum V_i$	Sum of item variance	1.741536191	
V_t	Variance of total score	4.179252442	
α	Cronbach’s alpha	.73	
Attitudes			
k	Number of items	5	Acceptable
$\sum V_i$	Sum of item variance	1.709651144	
V_t	Variance of total score	4.140767608	
α	Cronbach’s alpha	.73	
Concerns			
k	Number of items	5	Acceptable
$\sum V_i$	Sum of item variance	1.972055332	
V_t	Variance of total score	5.078257601	
α	Cronbach’s alpha	.76	

Selection of participants

This study was conducted in 31 schools representing all regions of India, viz., geographically spread from Amritsar to Trivandrum, and, from Bhuj to Shillong.

Sample size

G*Power calculated a sample size of 382, as given in figure 1.

Figure 1. Calculation of sample size for quantitative study

A total of 1,205 participants initially undertook the survey, all of whom completed it in full, yielding a completion rate of 100%. Following data cleaning procedures, including the removal of univariate outliers, 1,175 responses were deemed suitable for statistical analysis (N = 1,175). This final sample size

exceeds the a priori sample size estimate of 382 obtained using G*Power. Moreover, the achieved sample size is consistent with the values reported in the published sample size determination table presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Sample Size for ±3%, ±5%, ±7%, and ±10% Precision Levels where Confidence Level Is 95% and P=.5.

Size of Population	Sample Size (n) for Precision (ε) of:			
	±3%	±5%	±7%	±10%
500	a	222	145	83
600	a	240	152	86
700	a	255	158	88
800	a	267	163	89
900	a	277	166	90
1,000	a	286	169	91
2,000	714	333	185	95
3,000	811	353	191	97
4,000	870	364	194	98
5,000	909	370	196	98

6,000	938	375	197	98
7,000	959	378	198	99
8,000	976	381	199	99
9,000	989	383	200	99
10,000	1,000	385	200	99
15,000	1,034	390	201	99
20,000	1,053	392	204	100
25,000	1,064	394	204	100
50,000	1,087	397	204	100
100,000	1,099	398	204	100
>100,000	1,111	400	204	100
a = Assumption of normal population is poor (Yamane, 1967). The entire population should be sampled.				

Note: Adapted from Determining Sample Size (Morse, 2000)

Data Collection Methodology

Data were collected using online Google Forms, a cloud-based platform used for the design and administration of web-based questionnaires. This tool, developed by Google, is freely accessible and widely used for survey-based research. Upon accessing the survey link, participants were presented with an informed consent statement outlining the voluntary nature of participation, potential risks, and assurances of confidentiality. Demographic information, along with responses to the SACIE-R scale, was collected electronically.

Coding of Quantitative Data

Following data collection, responses were systematically coded into numerical values for analysis. For instance, teacher categories were coded as 1 for general teachers and 2 for special educators. Years of teaching experience were categorized and coded as follows: 0–4 years (1), 5–9 years (2), 10–14 years (3), 15–19 years (4), and above 20 years (5). Higher scores indicated more positive sentiments, attitudes, and concerns toward inclusive education.

Items in the SACIE-R scale that were negatively worded were reverse-coded to ensure consistency in interpretation. Specifically, responses were recoded such that “Strongly Agree” = 1, “Agree” = 2, “Disagree” = 3, and “Strongly Disagree” = 4. While items within the attitude’s subscale were positively framed, those within the sentiments and concerns subscales were negatively worded and therefore subjected to reverse coding during analysis. Scores above the midpoint value of 2.5 were interpreted as indicating a favourable disposition toward the inclusion of students with disabilities (Opoku et al., 2021).

Test for Normality of Quantitative Data

The distribution of the data was assessed for normality using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests. The results from both tests indicated a statistically significant deviation from normality, suggesting that the data did not follow a normal distribution. The outcomes of these normality tests for the scale scores are presented in table 2.

Table 2. Normality Test for Scale Scores (N=1175)

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistics				Shapiro-Wilk	
Scales	Statistics (D)	Statistics (K)	p	Statistics (W)	P
Sentiments	0.1316	4.5117	2.22e-16	0.9736	8.171e-14

Attitudes	0.1648	5.6493	3.331e-16	0.9543	0
Concerns	0.1247	4.2761	6.661e-16	0.9708	1.177e-14

Factor structure of the SACIE-R data

carried out by using SPSS 26 and AMOS 26. The model fit summary is as under (refer table 3): -

Confirmatory factor analysis to test for data fit of the expected factor structure of the SACIE-R scale was

**Table 3. Model fit summary
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)**

Model	RMSEA	LO 90	HI 90	PCLOSE
Default model	.064	.058	.069	.000
Independence model	.169	.164	.174	.000

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Default model	33	500.741	87	.000	5.756
Saturated model	120	.000	0		
Independence model	15	3621.538	105	.000	34.491

RMR, GFI

Model	RMR	GFI	AGFI	PGFI
Default model	.022	.941	.918	.682
Saturated model	.000	1.000		
Independence model	.090	.588	.529	.514

Baseline Comparisons

Model	NFI Delta1	RFI rho1	IFI Delta2	TLI rho2	CFI
Default model	.862	.833	.883	.858	.882
Saturated model	1.000		1.000		1.000
Independence model	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

The results for the CFA model indicated that overall, it is an acceptable model fit since GFI (.941) being more than .90 indicates a good fit (Ivey & Kline, 2010) as also RMSEA value (.064) is less than 0.07, which indicates an adequate data fit (Steiger, 2007). Even values of CFI (.882) and TLI (.858) are considered barely adequate. The Confirmatory factor analysis of the model is as given figure 2 under.

Figure 2. Confirmatory factor analysis of the model

Data Analysis

Demographic information of sample

The data analysis revealed that, of the 1,175 participants, 43 (3.66%) were special educators, while the remaining 1,132 (96.34%) were general teachers. Participants’ teaching experience ranged from 0–4 years (19.66%) to 20 years and above (18.38%). A total of 519 respondents (44.17%) reported prior experience working with CwSN.

The distribution of age groups varied from 20–29 years (14.98%) to 50–60 years (17.02%). Female participants constituted the majority (80.60%), compared to male participants (19.40%). Approximately 79% of the respondents held a Master’s degree. Additionally, 443 participants (37.70%) reported having received training in inclusive or special education. The frequency distributions for these variables are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Frequency Counts for Variables (N=1175)

Variable and category		%
Teacher Group		
General Teachers	1132	96.34
Special Educators	43	3.66

Years of Teaching Service		
0-4 years	231	19.66
5-9 years	286	24.34
10-14 years	265	22.55
15-19 years	177	15.06
Above 20years	216	18.38
Experience with CwSN		
Yes	519	44.17
No	459	39.06
Maybe	197	16.77
Age Group		
20-29 years	176	14.98
30-39 years	415	35.32
40-49 years	384	32.68
50-60 years	200	17.02
Gender		
Male	228	19.40
Female	947	80.60
Education		
Bachelor's degree	209	17.79
Master's degree	925	78.72
M Phil	17	1.45
Doctorate	24	2.04
Inclusive Education/ Special Education Training		
Yes	443	37.70
No	732	62.30

The findings of the present study indicate that teachers generally exhibit a positive orientation toward inclusive education (M = 2.89) (see Table 5).

Among the subscales, *sentiments* recorded the highest mean score (M = 3.00), suggesting that teachers are largely comfortable interacting with CwSN.

Specifically, respondents indicated that they are not apprehensive about engaging with such students ($M = 2.856$), maintaining eye contact ($M = 3.055$), or reflecting on the possibility of disability in themselves ($M = 3.044$). However, their responses reflected relative neutrality when interacting with individuals with severe physical disabilities ($M = 2.627$).

The *attitudes* subscale yielded the lowest mean score ($M = 2.557$), indicating comparatively limited readiness among teachers to fully embrace certain aspects of inclusion. For instance, teachers expressed lower willingness to include students requiring assistive communication technologies. In contrast, they demonstrated greater acceptance of students who experience difficulty in verbal expression ($M = 2.620$) and those who encounter challenges in examinations ($M = 3.011$). These findings are broadly consistent with earlier research (Agavelyan et al., 2020). Notably, however, teachers showed a relatively high level of willingness ($M = 3.144$) to accommodate

students requiring individualized curricula within regular classrooms.

The *concerns* subscale reported a mean value of 2.84, indicating moderate levels of concern. Teachers expressed apprehension regarding increased workload in inclusive settings ($M = 2.552$). At the same time, they reported comparatively lower concern about experiencing stress due to the presence of CwSN in their classrooms ($M = 3.029$). Respondents also indicated confidence in their knowledge and skills for teaching students with disabilities ($M = 2.927$) and their ability to provide adequate attention to all learners in an inclusive classroom ($M = 2.746$). A particularly positive finding was the belief that CwSN would be accepted by their peers ($M = 2.955$). These results align with findings from qualitative studies examining peer acceptance and the preparedness of general teachers for inclusive education.

Table 5. Means and standard deviations for scores on the SACIE-R Scale

Item	Mean	Standard deviation
The Sentiments subscale	3.00	.718
I am afraid to look a person with a disability straight in the face	3.055	.723
I tend to make contacts with people with disabilities brief and I finish them as quickly as possible	2.856	.710
I find it difficult to overcome my initial shock when meeting people with severe physical disabilities	2.627	.724
I dread the thought that I could eventually end up with a disability	3.422	.554
I would feel terrible if I had a disability	3.044	.615
The Attitudes subscale	2.84	.650
Students who frequently fail exams should be educated in regular classes	3.011	.720
Students who have difficulty expressing their thoughts verbally should be educated in regular classes	2.620	.703
Students who are inattentive should be educated in regular classes	2.870	.740
Students who need an individualized academic program should be educated in regular classes	3.144	.585

Students who require communicative technologies (for example Braille and sign language) should be educated in regular classes	2.557	.724
The Concerns subscale	2.84	.731
I am concerned that I will be more stressed if I have students with disabilities in my class	3.029	.622
I am concerned that students with disabilities will not be accepted by the rest of the class	2.955	.587
I am concerned that my workload will increase if I have students with disabilities in my class	2.552	.662
I am concerned that I do not have knowledge and skills required to teach students with disabilities	2.927	.628
I am concerned that it will be difficult to give appropriate attention to all students in an inclusive classroom	2.746	.635
Total SACIE-R	2.894	.324

According to the decision rule proposed by (Nachar, 2008), the null hypothesis is rejected when the absolute value of the calculated z exceeds or equals the critical (tabulated) z value. The Mann–Whitney U

test was conducted using XLSTAT, and the results were cross-validated using an online calculator available at Statistics Kingdom. The computed values are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Mann-Whitney Test for Scale Scores Based on Teacher Group (N =1175)

Teacher Group	n	M	SD	rs	U	z	p	Results
Sentiments								
General teachers	1132	2.994	0.410	0.49	17709	3.071	0.002131	Significant
Special educators	43	3.195	0.502					
Attitudes								
General teachers	1132	2.827	0.429	0.51	12370.5	5.574	2.482e-8	Significant
Special educators	43	3.223	0.424					
Concerns								
General teachers	1132	2.833	0.448	0.48	18204	2.837	0.004554	Significant
Special educators	43	3.042	0.487					

The results indicate statistically significant differences between general teachers and special educators across all three dimensions—sentiments, attitudes, and concerns.

For the *attitude's* subscale, the Mann–Whitney U test revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups. As the computed p -value is lower than the significance threshold ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis (H_1). Specifically, the p -value was 2.482×10^{-8} , indicating lesser probability of committing a Type I error. Lower p -values provide stronger evidence in support of the alternative hypothesis.

The test statistic ($Z = -5.5745$) falls outside the 95% acceptance interval $[-1.96, 1.96]$, further confirming the statistical significance of the result. Similarly, the obtained U value ($U = 12370.5$) lies outside the corresponding acceptance range $[20130.4949, 28545.5051]$. Overall, the test was statistically significant ($z [1175] = 5.574$, $p = 2.482 \times 10^{-8}$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis associated with the research question.

In summary, the findings demonstrate significant differences in sentiments, attitudes, and concerns between general teachers and special educators with respect to the implementation of inclusive education in India.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the present study indicate that teachers generally demonstrate a positive orientation toward inclusive education, as reflected in the overall mean scores across the SACIE-R dimensions. This aligns with prior research suggesting that educators are increasingly receptive to inclusive practices, although such receptivity is often nuanced and context-dependent. Notably, the *sentiments* dimension recorded the highest mean score, indicating that teachers are largely comfortable interacting with CwSN. This suggests that interpersonal apprehensions—often considered a primary barrier to inclusion—may be gradually diminishing, possibly due to increased awareness, exposure, and evolving societal attitudes toward disability.

However, the relatively lower mean score observed in the *attitude's* subscale highlights a degree of

ambivalence in fully embracing inclusive practices, particularly in instructional contexts requiring specialized pedagogical adaptations. Teachers expressed comparatively lower willingness to include students who require assistive communication technologies, which may reflect perceived inadequacies in training, resources, or institutional support. At the same time, their greater acceptance of students with less intensive support needs—such as those facing difficulties in verbal expression or examinations—indicates a tendency toward conditional acceptance. This finding underscores the persistent gap between conceptual endorsement of inclusion and its practical implementation in diverse classroom settings.

The *concerns* subscale revealed moderate levels of apprehension, particularly regarding increased workload. This concern is well-documented in the literature and reflects structural and systemic challenges associated with inclusive education, including large class sizes, limited support staff, and insufficient professional development opportunities. Interestingly, teachers reported relatively low levels of concern regarding stress, suggesting a degree of professional resilience or confidence in managing inclusive classrooms. Furthermore, respondents expressed belief in their own competence to teach students with disabilities and their ability to provide equitable attention to all learners. Such perceptions are encouraging, as teacher self-efficacy is a critical determinant of successful inclusive practice.

This study's comparison of general teachers and special educators is one of its main contributions. The findings repeatedly show that compared to regular instructors, special educators have noticeably more positive attitudes, sentiments, and worries regarding inclusive education. This result is in line with previous studies and could be explained by special educators' professional orientation toward working with CwSN, more exposure, and specialized training. Since general instructors are at the forefront of delivering inclusive education in mainstream classrooms, the statistically significant disparities across all three variables highlight the need of focused capacity-building programs.

These results have significant ramifications for practice and policy, especially in light of India's

commitment to inclusive education under national laws and international frameworks like SDG-4. Although legislative mandates have produced a favourable climate, the findings indicate that ongoing funding for teacher preparation, institutional support networks, and attitude change is necessary for successful implementation. Strengthening inclusive practices may be achieved by bridging the gap between general and special educators through co-teaching methods, collaborative models, and ongoing professional development.

CONCLUSION

The advancement of civic democracy is closely linked to the promotion of inclusive education (Brig (Dr) Sujay Ranjan Chaudhuri (Retd), 2026b). Its central objective is to transform schools into spaces characterized by both excellence and equity for all learners (Stepaniuk, 2019). Teachers occupy a pivotal role in fostering open and inclusive classroom environments that support the participation of all children (Costello & Boyle, 2013b). Owing to their critical influence, teachers' attitudes toward integration and inclusion have been the subject of extensive scholarly inquiry over several decades (Saloviita, 2020a). A substantial body of research further underscores the centrality of teachers in ensuring the successful implementation of inclusive education and in driving systemic educational transformation globally (Hooijer et al., 2021). Against this backdrop, the present study aimed to examine whether significant differences exist between general teachers and special educators in terms of their attitudes, sentiments, and concerns regarding the implementation of inclusive education in India.

The current study offers empirical evidence that, despite the fact that most instructors have good attitudes about inclusive education, there are notable distinctions in the attitudes, sentiments, and concerns of general teachers and special educators. Special educators constantly exhibit increasingly positive attitudes, underscoring the crucial role that education and experience play in influencing attitudes toward inclusion.

The results emphasize that the successful implementation of inclusive education requires more than just favourable attitudes. Even though educators

seem at ease working with CwSN, there are still difficulties converting these attitudes into inclusive teaching methods, especially in situations when specialist assistance is needed. The necessity for systemic solutions is further demonstrated by worries about workload and resource limitations.

Policymakers, educational institutions, and training organizations must prioritize comprehensive teacher preparation programs that address the cognitive and affective aspects of inclusion in light of these findings. Realizing the objectives of inclusive education in India requires boosting the skills and self-assurance of general instructors, encouraging cooperation with special educators, and guaranteeing sufficient institutional and infrastructure support.

Overall, by emphasizing the significance of teacher-related factors in influencing implementation outcomes, the study adds to the expanding corpus of work on inclusive education. By investigating long-term shifts in teacher attitudes and analysing the effects of focused interventions on inclusive classroom practices, future research may expand on these findings.

REFERENCES

1. Agavelyan, R. O., Aubakirova, S. D., Zhomartova, A. D., & Burdina, E. I. (2020). Teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education in Kazakhstan. *Integration of Education*, 24(1), 8–19. <https://doi.org/10.15507/1991-9468.098.024.202001.008-019>
2. Avramidis, E., Bayliss, P., & Burden, R. (2000). A survey into mainstream teachers' attitudes towards the inclusion of children with special educational needs in the ordinary school in one local education authority. *Educational Psychology*, 20(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/713663717>
3. Brig (Dr) Sujay Ranjan Chaudhuri (Retd). (2026a). Are Parents Ready to Embrace an Inclusive Model of Education: A Qualitative Study. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 1087–1096. <https://doi.org/10.21275/SR26217195900>
4. Brig (Dr) Sujay Ranjan Chaudhuri (Retd). (2026b). Exploring Attitudes, Concerns, and Sentiments of Special Educators towards the

- Inclusive Model of Education in India: A Qualitative Study. <https://doi.org/12.163022.Gj.2025.v19.02.015>
5. Costello, S., & Boyle, C. (2013a). Pre-service secondary teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 38(4), 129–143. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2013v38n4.8>
 6. Costello, S., & Boyle, C. (2013b). Pre-service secondary teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 38(4). <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2013v38n4.8>
 7. De Boer, A., Pijl, S. J., & Minnaert, A. (2011). Regular primary schoolteachers' attitudes towards inclusive education: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 15(3), 331–353. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110903030089>
 8. Ewing, D. L., Monsen, J. J., & Kielblock, S. (2018). Teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education: a critical review of published questionnaires. In *Educational Psychology in Practice* (Vol. 34, Number 2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/02667363.2017.1417822>
 9. Florian, L., & Spratt, J. (2013). Enacting inclusion: A framework for interrogating inclusive practice. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 28(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2013.778111>
 10. Forlin, C., Earle, C., Loreman, T., & Sharma, U. (2011). The Sentiments, Attitudes, and Concerns about Inclusive Education Revised (SACIE-R) Scale for Measuring Pre-Service Teachers' Perceptions about Inclusion. *Exceptionality Education International*, 21(3), 50–65. <https://doi.org/10.5206/eei.v21i3.7682>
 11. Garry Hornby. (2014). *Inclusive Special Education Evidence-Based Practices for Children with Special Needs and Disabilities*. Springer Science+Business Media.
 12. Hill, R. J., Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1977). Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research. *Contemporary Sociology*, 6(2), 244. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2065853>
 13. Hooijer, E. L., Van der Merwe, Dr. M., & Fourie, Dr. J. (2021). Symbolic Representations as Teachers Reflect on Inclusive Education in South Africa. *African Journal of Teacher Education*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.21083/ajote.v10i1.6549>
 14. Hussey, M., MacLachlan, M., & Mji, G. (2017). Barriers to the implementation of the health and rehabilitation articles of the United Nations convention on the rights of persons with disabilities in South Africa. *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 6(4), 207–218. <https://doi.org/10.15171/ijhpm.2016.117>
 15. Ivey, G. W., & Kline, T. J. B. (2010). Transformational and active transactional leadership in the Canadian military. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 31(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437731011039352>
 16. Livneh, H., Antonak, R. F., & Gerhardt, J. (2000). Multidimensional investigation of the structure of coping among people with amputations. *Psychosomatics*, 41(3). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.psy.41.3.235>
 17. Loreman, T., Forlin, C., & Sharma, U. (2007). An International Comparison of Pre-service Teacher Attitudes towards Inclusive Education. *Disability Studies Quarterly*, 27.
 18. Loreman, T., Sharma, U., & Forlin, C. (2013). Do pre-service teachers feel ready to teach in inclusive classrooms? A four country study of teaching self-efficacy. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 38(1). <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2013v38n1.10>
 19. Morse, J. M. (2000). Determining Sample Size. *Qualitative Health Research*, 10(1), 3–5. <https://doi.org/10.1177/104973200129118183>
 20. Nachar, N. (2008). The Mann-Whitney U: A Test for Assessing Whether Two Independent Samples Come from the Same Distribution. *Tutorials in Quantitative Methods for Psychology*, 4(1), 13–20. <https://doi.org/10.20982/tqmp.04.1.p013>
 21. NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY : Opportunities & Challenges A White Paper on India 's National Education Policy and Disability Inclusive Education National Centre for Promotion of Employment for Disabled People. (n.d.). 1–84.
 22. Nowicki, E. A., & Sandieson, R. (2002). A meta-analysis of school-age children's attitudes towards persons with physical or intellectual disabilities. *International Journal of Phytoremediation*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/1034912022000007270>

23. Opoku, M. P., Nketsia, W., Odame, L., & Agyei-Okyere, E. (2021). Predictors of the Attitudes of Preservice Teachers Toward Teaching Students With Down Syndrome in Regular Schools in Ghana. *Journal of Policy and Practice in Intellectual Disabilities*, 18(3). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jppi.12379>
24. Saloviita, T. (2020a). Attitudes of Teachers Towards Inclusive Education in Finland. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 64(2), 270–282. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2018.1541819>
25. Saloviita, T. (2020b). Teacher attitudes towards the inclusion of students with support needs. *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-3802.12466>
26. Schuelka, M., Braun, A., & Johnstone, C. (2020). Beyond Access and Barriers: Inclusive Education and Systems Change. *FIRE: Forum for International Research in Education*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.32865/fire202061198>
27. Shaffer, L., & Thomas-Brown, K. (2015a). Enhancing Teacher Competency through Co-Teaching and Embedded Professional Development. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v3i3.685>
28. Shaffer, L., & Thomas-Brown, K. (2015b). Enhancing Teacher Competency through Co-Teaching and Embedded Professional Development. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.11114/jets.v3i3.685>
29. Shields, P. A. (2020a). Differences between attitudes, concerns, and self-efficacy of secondary general and special education teachers towards inclusive education. *Dissertation Abstracts International Section A: Humanities and Social Sciences*, 81(10-A).
30. Shields, P. A. (2020b). Differences between attitudes, concerns, and self-efficacy of secondary general and special education teachers towards inclusive education. *Dissertation Abstracts International Section A: Humanities and Social Sciences*, 81(10-A).
31. Shutaleva, A., Martyushev, N., Nikonova, Z., Savchenko, I., & Kukartsev, V. (2023). Sustainability of Inclusive Education in Schools and Higher Education: Teachers and Students with Special Educational Needs.
32. Stepaniuk, I. (2019). Inclusive education in Eastern European countries: a current state and future directions. In *International Journal of Inclusive Education* (Vol. 23, Number 3, pp. 328–352). <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2018.1430180>

HOW TO CITE: Sujay Ranjan Chaudhuri*, Attitudes, Sentiments, And Concerns In Inclusive Education: A Quantitative Causal-Comparative Analysis Of General And Special Educators In India, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2026, 3 (5), 448-461. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20137296>